

RESO

WP2-RP02: Metadata Report

Version: 1.0.1

Date: 2021-03-01

Element	Description
Title	RESO metadata report
Creator	Dr Joe Day, Dr Grant Wilson
Subject	Metadata
Description	A brief overview for the RESO project on metadata and its use
Publisher	Energy Informatics Group, University of Birmingham
Contributor	
Date	2021-03-01
Type	Text
Format	application/pdf
Identifier	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4607291
Source	Descriptions of Dublin core elements taken in part from https://www.dublincore.org/specifications/dublin-core/usageguide/elements/
Language	en-GB
Relation	
Coverage	n/a
Rights	CC-BY-4.0
Dissemination / confidentiality	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Public/ RESO webpage/ Social media <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> ERIS/ IUK Consortiums <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Funder <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Consortium <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Internal

Smart Local Energy System Design

Change log	Updated by	Date
0.0.1 – Initial draft	Dr Joe Day	2020-03-31
1.0.1 – Updated report with mention of coversheets for RESO outputs	Dr Joe Day, Dr Grant Wilson	2021-03-01

SUMMARY

A short document on the background to Metadata for datasets and outputs of the RESO project.

The project aim is to use a cover page for all shared outputs from the RESO project (whether internal or external). The cover page is based on the DublinCore Metadata standard that is presented in this document, and meets one of the recommendations of the Energy Data Taskforce to make data (and outputs) more machine readable and searchable.

The cover page should be published even when the actual report or data cannot due to confidentiality, *i.e.* the cover page provides a machine readable overview of the output regardless of whether the output is published or not.

Metadata and Dublin Core

In projects that work with a lot of datasets, it is essential to build an accompanying catalogue of metadata (e.g. data about the data) through a common and standardised procedure. This is in line with Recommendation 3 of the Energy Data Taskforce report¹.

1.1 What is metadata?

Metadata gives us more information about the data in our collection. It can be thought of intuitively as the answers to one or more questions someone might have about the data starting with: ‘Who?’, ‘What?’, ‘When?’, ‘Where?’, ‘Why?’, ‘Which?’ and ‘How?’.

Considering the simple example of the collection of photographs below as our **data**:

The **metadata** describing this data could look something like this table:

Place taken	Date taken	Camera used	Photographer
Liverpool	20/05/2012	iPhone 8	S. Gerrard

¹ Energy Systems Catapult. (2019). Energy Data Taskforce: A Strategy for a Modern Digitalised Energy System. Available from: <https://es.catapult.org.uk/news/energy-data-taskforce-report/>

Smart Local Energy System Design

Manchester	13/08/2014	Canon EOS	P. Scholes
Barcelona	27/09/2015	iPhone 5s	L. Messi
New York	01/02/2009	Sony Cybershot	D. Trump

1.2 The benefits of good metadata

Creating metadata along with your data increases its visibility and value to the target audience. This is particularly important for the energy sector where it is recommended a Data Catalogue under the principle of ‘Presumed Openness’ should be established to help researchers and innovators alike (Energy Systems Catapult, 2019).

Good metadata enables large numbers of datasets to be processed together (either by humans or machines). For example, this could mean auditing the sets (to improve quality/consistency), finding links across datasets or enabling a user-friendly search/filtering process (Baker, 2011).

To achieve these, it helps to have the metadata of each dataset in the same form, so that they are *interoperable*, meaning the same operation can be performed on each dataset’s metadata (which is necessary for any computer based comparison or sorting algorithm). As a result, metadata is usually presented as a markup language file (such as .xml). In the RESO project, all outputs should have a DublinCore compliant table as a cover sheet.

1.3 Dublin Core

Although the previous example of the photographs tells us some useful information about the data, it is not a standardised procedure (the choice of descriptors in the table were chosen arbitrarily). One such standard procedure for handling metadata is the Dublin Core (named after Dublin, Ohio not the Irish capital), a system for describing data using 15 core elements. This is the metadata standard recommended by the Energy Data Taskforce for its Data Catalogue due to its relative simplicity and option to extend the number of descriptive elements (beyond 15) in the future, if needed. Furthermore, a common glossary would be created to help data categorisation and government/Ofgem licensing conditions could be used to compel metadata registration among market actors.

The 15 core elements in Dublin Core are as follows:

- Title
- Creator
- Subject
- Description
- Publisher
- Contributor
- Date

Regional Energy System Operator (RESO)

Smart Local Energy System Design

- Type
- Format
- Identifier
- Source
- Language
- Relation
- Coverage
- Rights

Smart Local Energy System Design

Formal definitions of each of these and best practice guidance can be found at:

<https://www.dublincore.org/specifications/dublin-core/usageguide/elements/>

Note elements 16-22 on that webpage are for use in Qualified Dublin Core and we are only using Simple Dublin Core, so can neglect them. Of elements 1-15, some are self-explanatory whilst others at first seem to overlap (not all 15 elements have to be used in every case), but the following thought process may be helpful for each element.

Title: Self-explanatory (the name of the resource). Usually the writing in bold/large font at the top of the webpage from where the file was downloaded or the front cover if a report. Alternatively, if the dataset is synthetic or not publicly available, then choose a logical, concise name for its title.

Creator: Who created the resource (e.g. the primary author(s))? Usually an organisation (such as BEIS or the Office for National Statistics) or individual author.

Subject: A selection of specific key words associated with the data. Usually from the title or abstract. Recommended best practice to use a formal classification scheme (I imagine this will be role of the Energy Data Taskforce's common glossary).

Description: Usually the abstract or paragraph beneath the title can be copy and pasted here. If no suitable paragraph exists, a short descriptive summary (using full sentences and clear vocabulary) is acceptable.

Publisher: Who made the resource available? Usually the government department that released the statistics or the organisation commissioned for a report. If the Creator and Publisher are the same, best practice is to just use a Publisher for organisations and Creator for individuals.

Contributor: Who contributed to the resource? Sometimes left blank if it is clear who the Publisher and Creator are, or as an alternative to both (if they are both unknown), or to list secondary individuals/organisations who contributed to the resource but not by as much as the creator.

Date: The date for when the resource was made available. Just the year is acceptable but best practice for full dates is to use the ISO-8601 style e.g. YYYY-MM-DD.

Type: What is the type of data? There is a list of standard vocabulary on the website. We will mostly use 'Dataset' for spreadsheets, 'Text' for written reports or 'Collection' for a collection of different datasets.

Format: The format of the file. Best practice is to use the list of Internet Media Types. Mostly we will only need to use two of these: 'text/csv' for csv files or 'application/pdf' for written reports. Sometimes excel files can be more complicated but their format can be found by right clicking on the file in its folder, going to Properties then the Details tab and copying and pasting from the 'Content type'.

Smart Local Energy System Design

Identifier: How to find the resource? Usually use the URL of the webpage for publicly available datasets/reports.

Source: The resource from which this piece of data was derived. Only applies when the dataset is a subset of a wider collection. Best practice to add a URL as a source as well.

Language: What language is the data in? Best practice to use two letter codes. Almost always our outputs will be 'en-GB'.

Relation: A list of any related datasets. This could be other members of a collection's subset or references to other documents cited within a report. Standard vocabulary on website to describe types of Relations. Most common are: References/IsReferencedBy, HasPart/IsPartOf*, HasFormat/IsFormatOf and HasVersion/IsVersionOf (*IsPartOf is usually used alongside Source). Also – can be left blank

Coverage: Where and when does the data cover in terms of geographical area and time periods analysed? For example, 'England & Wales' and '2005-2017'.

Rights: Explains who owns any rights over the resource. For a lot of publicly available data this will be 'UK Open Government Licence (OGL) v3.0'. For privately held data this could be explained in a brief statement or a URL pointing to one.

Metadata is typically presented in the form of a markup language such as **xml**. Thankfully, there is a nifty tool which allows you to input each element and get the xml code generated for you (it's the first web page returned when you Google 'Dublin core generator').

https://nsteffel.github.io/dublin_core_generator/generator_nq.html

Just fill out as many boxes as you need, then click all tick boxes except the bottom one (we only need the namespace for standard Dublin Core not qualified) and hit Generate Metadata! The code will display in the Output box at the bottom of the page. Unfortunately trying to download the xml file returns a 405 error, but you can get around this by copy and pasting the text from the Output box into notepad, then save as using the file extension '.xml'. Congratulations, you now have a robust metadata file to accompany your dataset!

Bibliography and other useful links

Energy Systems Catapult. (2019). Energy Data Taskforce: A Strategy for a Modern Digitalised Energy System. Available from:
<https://es.catapult.org.uk/news/energy-data-taskforce-report/>

Baker, Mark. (2011). 'The Meaning of Metadata'. Available from:
<https://everypageispageone.com/2011/05/20/the-meaning-of-metadata/>

Regional Energy System Operator (RESO)

Smart Local Energy System Design

Jeffrey Pomerantz – Metadata MOOC 2-3: Dublin Core Elements
<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=5HJVfp5c0kE>

Simple Dublin Core Generator

https://nsteffel.github.io/dublin_core_generator/generator_nq.html

Dublin Core Elements Guide (only need 4.1-4.15)

<https://www.dublincore.org/specifications/dublin-core/usageguide/elements/>

2 EXAMPLE WITH BEIS POSTCODE LEVEL GAS STATISTICS 2018 TO CREATE METADATA IN XML

*Note - XML does not like '&' in its text and will return an error if one is present, so use e.g. Energy **and** Industrial Strategy instead of Energy **&** Industrial Strategy.

Also remember Dublin Core is only a guide with **recommended** best practices (i.e. no compulsion to use all 15 elements or always follow the guide verbatim, although consistency is always aimed for). Hence its flexibility and relative simplicity to new users.

Input

Title?
[+][-]

Postcode level gas statistics: 2018 (experimental)

Creator?
[+][-]

Oliver Hendey

Subject?
[+][-]

Gas

Gas consumption

Domestic

Postcode level

Description?
[+][-]

This dataset contains the 2018 statistics of domestic gas consumption for postcodes in Great Britain.

Publisher?
[+][-]

Department for Business, Energy and Industrial Stra

Contributor?
[+][-]

Adam Bricknell

Date?
[+][-]

2019-12-19

Type?
[+][-]

Collection

Format?
[+][-]

Identifier?
[+][-]

<https://www.gov.uk/government/statistics/postcode-le>

Source?
[+][-]

Sub-national gas consumption data

<https://www.gov.uk/government/collections/sub-natio>

Smart Local Energy System Design

Language? [+] [-]
en-GB

Relation? [+] [-]
IsPartOf Sub-national gas consumption data
HasPart Experimental postcode domestic gas stat
HasPart Footnotes for postcode level statistics

Coverage? [+] [-]
Great Britain
2018

Rights? [+] [-]
UK Open Government Licence (OGL) v3.0

Output Options

Display output as: XML ▾

- Include standard XML version/encoding declaration.
- Include root element and namespace.
Desired root element: metadata
- Include namespace reference for standard Dublin Core (DC Elements).
- Include namespace reference for qualified Dublin Core (DC Terms).

Generate Metadata! [Reset Page](#)

Output

```
<?xml version="1.0" encoding="UTF-8"?>
<metadata
  xmlns:xsi="http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema-instance"
  xmlns:dc="http://purl.org/dc/elements/1.1/">
  <dc:title>Postcode level gas statistics: 2018 (experimental)</dc:title>
  <dc:creator>Oliver Hendey</dc:creator>
  <dc:subject>Gas</dc:subject>
  <dc:subject>Gas consumption</dc:subject>
  <dc:subject>Domestic</dc:subject>
  <dc:subject>Postcode level</dc:subject>
  <dc:description>This dataset contains the 2018 statistics of domestic gas consumption for postcodes in Great Britain.
</dc:description>
  <dc:publisher>Department for Business, Energy and Industrial Strategy</dc:publisher>
  <dc:contributor>Adam Bricknell</dc:contributor>
  <dc:date>2019-12-19</dc:date>
  <dc:type>Collection</dc:type>
  <dc:identifier>https://www.gov.uk/government/statistics/postcode-level-gas-statistics-2018-experimental</dc:identifier>
  <dc:source>Sub-national gas consumption data</dc:source>
```

Smart Local Energy System Design

Click Generate Metadata! Then copy and paste everything from the output box into notepad.

Next save the file with an .xml file extension (on the Save As menu, make sure to save as type 'All files' and check that the encoding is set to UTF-8).

Now when you open the xml with any internet browser, you should get the following:

```
<?xml version="1.0" encoding="UTF-8"?>
- <metadata xmlns:dc="http://purl.org/dc/elements/1.1/" xmlns:xsi="http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema-instance">
  <dc:title>Postcode level gas statistics: 2018 (experimental)</dc:title>
  <dc:creator>Oliver Henley</dc:creator>
  <dc:subject>Gas</dc:subject>
  <dc:subject>Gas consumption</dc:subject>
  <dc:subject>Domestic</dc:subject>
  <dc:subject>Postcode level</dc:subject>
  <dc:description>This dataset contains the 2018 statistics of domestic gas consumption for postcodes in Great Britain. </dc:description>
  <dc:publisher>Department for Business, Energy and Industrial Strategy</dc:publisher>
  <dc:contributor>Adam Bricknell</dc:contributor>
  <dc:date>2019-12-19</dc:date>
  <dc:type>Collection</dc:type>
  <dc:identifier>https://www.gov.uk/government/statistics/postcode-level-gas-statistics-2018-experimental</dc:identifier>
  <dc:source>Sub-national gas consumption data</dc:source>
  <dc:source>https://www.gov.uk/government/collections/sub-national-gas-consumption-data</dc:source>
  <dc:language>en-GB</dc:language>
  <dc:relation>IsPartOf Sub-national gas consumption data</dc:relation>
  <dc:relation>HasPart Experimental postcode domestic gas statistics 2018</dc:relation>
  <dc:relation>HasPart Footnotes for postcode level consumption</dc:relation>
  <dc:coverage>Great Britain</dc:coverage>
  <dc:coverage>2018</dc:coverage>
  <dc:rights>UK Open Government Licence (OGL) v3.0</dc:rights>
</metadata>
```

This is the final product, a metadata file made using Dublin Core.

Because the dataset here is actually a collection, containing two subsets (the csv file containing the gas consumption data and accompanying footnotes), it is necessary to repeat the procedure for each (.xml files shown below).

Note, if making small changes to an .xml or constructing a metadata file that has a lot of similar elements, you can save time by editing the file in notepad, as opposed to typing everything in the generator again.

Smart Local Energy System Design

```
<?xml version="1.0" encoding="UTF-8"?>
- <metadata xmlns:dc="http://purl.org/dc/elements/1.1/" xmlns:xsi="http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema-instance">
  <dc:title>Experimental postcode domestic gas statistics 2018</dc:title>
  <dc:creator>Oliver Hendey</dc:creator>
  <dc:subject>Gas</dc:subject>
  <dc:subject>Gas consumption</dc:subject>
  <dc:subject>Domestic</dc:subject>
  <dc:subject>Postcode level</dc:subject>
  <dc:description>Data for total domestic gas consumption, number of meters, mean and median consumption for postcodes in Great Britain.
    Excludes postcodes that are disclousive</dc:description>
  <dc:publisher>Department for Business, Energy and Industrial Strategy</dc:publisher>
  <dc:contributor>Adam Bricknell</dc:contributor>
  <dc:date>2019-12-19</dc:date>
  <dc:type>Dataset</dc:type>
  <dc:format>text/csv</dc:format>
  <dc:identifier>https://www.gov.uk/government/uploads/system/uploads/attachment_data/file/853776/Experimental_postcode_domestic_gas_sta
  <dc:source>Postcode level gas statistics: 2018 (experimental)</dc:source>
  <dc:source>https://www.gov.uk/government/statistics/postcode-level-gas-statistics-2018-experimental</dc:source>
  <dc:language>en-GB</dc:language>
  <dc:relation>IsPartOf Sub-national gas consumption data</dc:relation>
  <dc:relation>IsPartOf Postcode level gas statistics: 2018 (experimental)</dc:relation>
  <dc:coverage>Great Britain</dc:coverage>
  <dc:coverage>2018</dc:coverage>
  <dc:rights>UK Open Government Licence (OGL) v3.0</dc:rights>
</metadata>
```

Note this time the Type and Format have changed, the Identifier line has not been fully shown to improve readability and the Relation HasPart has changed to IsPartOf.

```
<?xml version="1.0" encoding="UTF-8"?>
- <metadata xmlns:dc="http://purl.org/dc/elements/1.1/" xmlns:xsi="http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema-instance">
  <dc:title>Footnotes for postcode level consumption</dc:title>
  <dc:creator>Oliver Hendey</dc:creator>
  <dc:subject>Electricity</dc:subject>
  <dc:subject>Electricity consumption</dc:subject>
  <dc:subject>Standard electricity</dc:subject>
  <dc:subject>Economy 7 electricity</dc:subject>
  <dc:subject>Postcode level</dc:subject>
  <dc:subject>Gas</dc:subject>
  <dc:subject>Gas consumption</dc:subject>
  <dc:subject>Domestic</dc:subject>
  <dc:description>Explains which data is excluded and other issues the user should note</dc:description>
  <dc:publisher>Department for Business, Energy and Industrial Strategy</dc:publisher>
  <dc:contributor>Adam Bricknell</dc:contributor>
  <dc:date>2019-12-19</dc:date>
  <dc:type>Text</dc:type>
  <dc:format>application/vnd.openxmlformats-officedocument.spreadsheetml.sheet</dc:format>
  <dc:identifier>https://assets.publishing.service.gov.uk/government/uploads/system/uploads/attachment_data/file/853787/Footnotes-for-
  <dc:source>Postcode level electricity statistics: 2018 (experimental)</dc:source>
  <dc:source>https://www.gov.uk/government/statistics/postcode-level-electricity-statistics-2018-experimental</dc:source>
  <dc:language>en-GB</dc:language>
  <dc:relation>IsPartOf Sub-national electricity consumption data</dc:relation>
  <dc:relation>IsPartOf Postcode level electricity statistics: 2018 (experimental)</dc:relation>
  <dc:relation>IsPartOf Postcode level gas statistics: 2018 (experimental)</dc:relation>
  <dc:relation>References Sub-national methodology and guidance booklet 2019</dc:relation>
  <dc:relation>References Regional and local authority electricity consumption statistics</dc:relation>
  <dc:relation>References Regional and local authority gas consumption statistics</dc:relation>
  <dc:coverage>Great Britain</dc:coverage>
  <dc:coverage>2018</dc:coverage>
  <dc:rights>UK Open Government Licence (OGL) v3.0</dc:rights>
</metadata>
```

Note more Subject key words and Relation elements are present because these footnotes also accompany the 2018 BEIS postcode level electricity consumption statistics. Also note, this is an xlsx file not a csv, so a different format has been used. Good practice is to make a folder for each data collection, then store each metadata file inside it. Finally note, the Relation element may span across different collections (as for the reason above).